

PRO-CLIMATE

Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change

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D7.1 Publicity and Dissemination Plan first version

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Contributor(s)	All partners	
Reviewer(s)	Pilar Muñoz Romero (DB)	Catalin Anton (ATU)
Approved by	Iason Tamiakis (Tero)	
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The **PRO-CLIMATE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 COO	TERO MONOPROSOPI IKE	TERO	EL
2 BEN	ATLANTIC TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	ATU	IE
3 BEN	INSTITOUTO SYNETAIRISTIKIS IGESIAS KAI SYNERGASIAS ASTIKI MI KerdoskopiKI ETAIREIA	Co-op	EL
4 BEN	UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	UiB	NO
5 BEN	UNIVERSITAET LEIPZIG	ULEI	DE
6 BEN	NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE AS	NORCE	NO
7 BEN	FUNDACION CARTIF	CARTIF	ES
8 BEN	DIPUTACION PROVINCIAL DE BADAJOZ	DB	ES
9 BEN	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	PL
10 BEN	COVENTRY UNIVERSITY	CU	UK

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Funded under European Union's Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme, the PRO-CLIMATE project aims to support communities to proactively adapt to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. To achieve this, PRO- CLIMATE will identify social tipping points and policy actions that enable systemic transformation to be achieved across social systems. PRO-CLIMATE will adopt an approach guided by the concept of systems thinking, which views communities as complex systems that are interconnected and influenced by multiple factors, socio-economic and environmental. By understanding and leveraging their dynamics, it will then develop strategies and interventions that promote social transformation and behavioural change. This will result in a robust framework for designing effective methodologies and tools to foster proactively adaptive behaviours and facilitate transformative changes.

The current document with the title "D7.1 Publicity and Dissemination Plan first version" defines the communication and dissemination strategy of the project, outlines the methods, tools and channels to be employed throughout the project's duration, describes the actions that partners will undertake and specifies the audience that the activities will be addressed to. It also includes a calendar of dissemination and communication activities and a tentative Action Plan. Finally, it defines the way that the project's dissemination and communication activities will be monitored and evaluated.

D7.1 is a public deliverable, part of "WP7 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation" and includes information about the project's scope as well as a short description of WP7 in order to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the DoA and the other WP7 deliverables is requested from the reader.

1 Introduction

1.1 The PRO-CLIMATE Project

The PRO-CLIMATE (Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change) project aims to support communities to proactively adapt to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE will identify social tipping points and policy actions that enable systemic transformation to be achieved across social systems. PRO-CLIMATE will adopt an approach guided by the concept of systems thinking, which views communities as complex systems that are interconnected and influenced by multiple factors, socio-economic and environmental. By understanding and leveraging their dynamics, it will then develop strategies and interventions that promote social transformation and behavioural change. This will result in a robust framework for designing effective methodologies and tools to foster proactively adaptive behaviours and facilitate transformative changes. A set of diverse (in terms of climate change problems and socio-economic contexts) case studies across Europe will be an instrumental tool for the co-creation, validation, and upscaling of this framework by running living labs and bringing stakeholders together to understand community governance and institutional structures, and to also pilot and validate the project's behavioural change activities. The outputs of PRO-CLIMATE include:

- a. the identification of key components of climate adaptation systems, their interactions, systemic interdependencies and trade-offs,
- b. the design, implementation, and evaluation of a living lab framework,
- c. the identification of social tipping points and leverage actions for policy makers,
- d. the development of a multi agent computer model for European socio-ecological systems to allow a realistic analysis of existing and future policy scenarios likely to produce systemic transformations, and
- e. policy recommendations to accelerate systemic change.

1.2 Description of WP7

WP7 incorporates PRO-CLIMATE activities related to publicity/awareness of the project, dissemination of results and relevant communication with external stakeholders/interested parties. These publicity and dissemination activities have been designed to reflect the project's needs and characteristics and are closely related to the post-project continuation and sustainability plans. It also collects lessons learned and obtains feedback from a broader network of projects through clustering with other EU projects. The specific tasks of WP7 are the following:

- Task 7.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.2: Dissemination activities (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.3: Communication activities (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.4: Cooperation and clustering with other projects (M1 – M36)
- Task 7.5: Exploitation prospects (M4 – M36)

1.3 Purpose and scope

The document provides the strategy for disseminating and communicating the PRO-CLIMATE project. This strategy is of utmost importance for ensuring the best possible impact of the project. This deliverable serves as a reference point for project partners towards the planned actions, assist the consortium to monitor the activities realization and update it accordingly when and where necessary based on the project's needs (with a final version D7.2 being prepared on M24).

D7.1 defines in a clear manner the approach that will be followed and establishes a common understanding amongst the consortium. Overall, the expected result of this deliverable is to create the plan to achieve significant awareness of the project's activities, active engagement of the necessary stakeholders and prepare the ground for the sustainability of the results beyond the EC funding.

1.4 Structure of the document

Section 2 describes in detail the dissemination and communication strategy of the project, outlines the methods, tools and channels to be employed throughout the project's duration, describes the actions that partners will undertake and specifies the audience that the activities will be addressed to. Section 3 presents the planned dissemination and communication activities, as well as the objectives to evaluate the success of the dissemination and communication strategy. Section 4 presents the calendar of activities that is a summary of the planned dissemination and communication actions to be performed by the PRO-CLIMATE consortium. Finally, Section 5 elaborates a specific evaluation strategy to monitor the dissemination and communication efforts and targets to reach.

1.5 Relationship with other PRO-CLIMATE deliverables

As all WP7 actions are interlinked, the current deliverable D7.1 is related with the other WP7 deliverables and the table below describes the dependencies and relations.

Table 1: Relationships with other PRO-CLIMATE deliverables

WP7 Deliverables	Dependencies and Relation
D7.2 Publicity and Dissemination Plan Final	D7.2 is an updated version of the current document that will be delivered on M24 of the project. During these 18 months from the delivery of D7.1 on M6 to the delivery of the updated version of D7.2, the Dissemination and Communication plan will be monitored and updated on a regular basis with the objective to make sure that the appropriate target messages are being reached to the appropriate audiences and the project is maximizing its impact.
D7.3 Dissemination & Communication Impact Report Interim version	D7.3 will provide a report about the overall progress of WP7 from M1 to M18, with emphasis on the dissemination and communication activities performed during this period, the benefits of the various stakeholders involved, the synergies developed with existing initiatives, the roadmap for expansion and the guide for replication of research and services.
D7.4 Dissemination & Communication Impact Report Final version	D7.4 will provide a report about the overall progress of WP7 from M19 to M36, with emphasis on the dissemination and communication activities performed during this period, the benefits of the various stakeholders involved, the synergies developed with existing initiatives, the roadmap for expansion and the guide for replication of the conducted research and offered services.

2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy

The dissemination and communication activities of PRO-CLIMATE aim to raise awareness regarding the project among the target audiences of specific stakeholder groups that constitute the project's community, thus maximising the outreach of the project's activities and results. The goal is to ensure that adequate information and key messages are shared with the appropriate audiences on a timely basis utilising the most effective channels and methods.

To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE's dissemination and communication strategy needs to answer some key questions that will guide the dissemination and communication activities of the consortium. These questions are:

- **Why** to disseminate and communicate i.e. what are the contractual obligations of the PRO-CLIMATE consortium in terms of dissemination and communication?
- **What** to disseminate and communicate i.e. what is the content and the key messages that should be communicated to PRO-CLIMATE's target audience?
- **When** to disseminate and communicate i.e. what is the suggested timeline of the dissemination and communication activities in order to increase the impact of the project?
- **To whom** to disseminate and communicate i.e. what is the most relevant stakeholders that should be informed about PRO-CLIMATE activities?
- **How** to disseminate and communicate i.e. what are the dissemination and communication methods, tools and channels that will be used during the project to increase the PRO-CLIMATE's impact.

The following sub-sections elaborate on the enlisted questions to provide a detailed overview about the PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication plan.

2.1 Why to disseminate and communicate?

All PRO-CLIMATE partners are involved in the dissemination and communication efforts and need to engage in dissemination and communication activities to foster awareness, transfer key messages and achieve impact, especially within their own countries and communities. The rationale for a carefully designed dissemination and communication plan is based on the requirements for attaining the maximum possible impact for the project by reaching a variety of audiences and communicating the right message to the right audience, as derived from the **dissemination and communication objectives**, the **contractual obligations** and the **project's overall goals**.

2.1.1 Dissemination and communication objectives

The objectives of the PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication strategy are formed to jointly satisfy the following needs:

- **Ecosystem building:** PRO-CLIMATE aims to build a strong ecosystem, bringing together all relevant stakeholders providing the basis for successful exploitation of the ecosystem towards sustainable transformation in the field of climate adaptation and resilience.
- **Engagement of stakeholders:** to achieve its objectives, PRO-CLIMATE needs to engage with different stakeholders which will act as potential contributors to the development, evaluation, uptake, and exploitation of its outcomes. PRO-CLIMATE needs to identify ways for encouraging their participation to project's actions on a systematic and regular basis.
- **Awareness building:** to secure a certain level of impact and promote a European collaborative approach on increasing knowledge and maximising the understanding of social transformation and behavioural change towards climate resilience, it is crucial for PRO-CLIMATE to work towards the cultivation of its awareness status in the diverse environments of the target audiences.
- **Feedback extraction:** as PRO-CLIMATE is a multidisciplinary project, it is expected to produce a series of reports and tools. It is important to disseminate such materials towards target audiences that will grasp such knowledge and provide valuable critical insights about

it. This will also ensure social acceptance and social relevance of the project's activities and results.

- **Exploitation of project results:** it is important to support the exploitation prospects of PRO-CLIMATE by disseminating the project's key exploitable results through adapted communication materials and appropriate dissemination means.

2.1.2 Contractual obligations

According to the PRO-CLIMATE Grant Agreement, the consortium is obliged to disseminate and communicate the progress and findings of the project to relevant stakeholder groups and the public in general. More specifically:

- **Article 17.1:** Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner. Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority.
- **Article 17.2:** Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 1: The EU emblem

2.1.3 WP7 goals

Some key elements that are described in WP7 activities of the PRO-CLIMATE Description of Action are presented below:

- The **Dissemination and Communication plan** will detail audience/ target groups, publicity and dissemination strategy with quantified and verifiable objectives, means to reach, actions, templates and channels to use, relevant timetable, indicators/ means of verification of the dissemination impact.
- The **PRO-CLIMATE website and social networking presence** will act as a major project publicity and dissemination platform. The PRO-CLIMATE consortium will also develop and actively operate project pages in Facebook, X, LinkedIn, and any other social networking platform deemed appropriate to boost publicity and user-friendly interaction.
- Two **PRO-CLIMATE videos** will be produced (around 3 minutes each) to be used as a powerful and of high-added value awareness creation and publicity tool. The first video (around M7-M9) will present the project rationale and challenges, showcasing the problem

and describing the envisioned solution. The second video (around M31-M33) will present an overview of the needs and a demonstration of the PRO-CLIMATE solutions under various scenarios taken from the case studies.

- PRO-CLIMATE will develop and register a **unique replicable process**, which supports sustainable change through the identification and sharing of good practices for other projects in the field of climate resilience and more widely, through the targeted workshops and training sessions aiming to leave its strong footprint in local communities and key stakeholders not only in areas where the case studies will take place but to a broader extent.
- PRO-CLIMATE will design and produce a variety of **promotional material**, including infographics, in electronic and hard-copy format, as well as give-away 'gadgets' to attract the attention and interest of its targeted groups. The consortium will avoid unnecessary printing/ use of paper.
- Major **PRO-CLIMATE dissemination events** will be the PRO-CLIMATE workshops and final conference. Other dissemination events and activities will include case studies workshops, scientific publications and presentations (in journals/ periodicals, conferences, etc.), presentations of PRO-CLIMATE results in relevant international, European and national/ local events, presentations and discussions in web-forums and communities, etc.
- As a major element of dissemination, PRO-CLIMATE consortium will work towards **publishing the project's results** in leading cross-disciplinary journals, in an attempt to reach diverse stakeholders groups, including scientists, practitioners, and policy makers. While the results from many case studies will be suitable for strong stand-alone papers, the main emphasis will be on producing synthetic, high-impact outputs that integrate material across projects/work-packages.
- A **publicity campaign** within the earlier stages of the project (to create and increase general project awareness), as well as targeted activities (at a later stage) to promote PRO-CLIMATE activities and events.
- Production of the necessary **Press Releases** in regard to the project's progress and activities.
- PRO-CLIMATE will build a **network of EU projects** and set up a knowledge sharing and transfer mechanism to ensure long- term impact and sustainability of the network's projects.
- Special attention will be given to the **Mission on Adaptation**, the related Climate Change projects and its implementation platform as well as the community of practice.

2.2 To whom to disseminate?

In order to be effective, the project's dissemination and communication strategy is selective about the choice of audience and strategic about its approach to that audience. PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication plan targets various stakeholders from different organisational, economic, and social contexts. Since the proposal phase, the consortium has worked towards identifying the target audiences. More specifically, the core group of stakeholders is comprised of:

Table 2: PRO-CLIMATE stakeholders

Target Group	Description / Details	Interest in the project
<p>Policymakers and funding Organisations</p>	<p>Policymakers at European, national or regional level, local/regional public authorities</p>	<p>Evidence-based policy guidance.</p> <p>Social tipping points and leverage actions.</p> <p>Evaluation of the project's factors which influence governance policies, foster behavioural change and resilience as well as attitudes at individual level.</p>

		The TrasnCliR Tool to be developed utilising the MACM of WP5. This will assist policymakers in decision planning processes.
NGOs and other local groups and local communities	Any organisation dealing with environmental and social aspects as well as relevant citizen groups	Use of citizen science and data to raise awareness through the proposed methodology. Dedicated activities such as workshops and meetings with organisations and local communities.
SMEs, Civic Society and local industries	Any SME, civic society group, and local industries representatives that influence climate policy actions or are directly affected by the climate conditions in their area.	Participation in the project's activities, training and workshops. They will also take advantage of the project's outcomes.
Researchers, innovators and practitioners	Researchers and innovators working in universities, research and technology centers, practitioners, R&D departments of industry, academia in general, active professionals in the field of climate resilience.	Learning from the project's outcomes. Design of material based on their needs. Use the replicable methods of the project. Educate future innovators. Compile research in promising areas and advance real-life cases through the re-use of the project's results. Practitioners will be empowered with methods and mechanisms to lower social and behavioural barriers and better understand societal implications.
Chambers of Commerce, SMEs and Cluster Networks	Relevant fact sheets, publications, educational and business blogs and specialised websites.	Understand the benefits offered by PRO-CLIMATE. Engagement in liaison activities and exploitation of knowledge created by the project. Learning methodology on how to exploit opportunities on promoting climate resilience.
General Public	General public and anyone interested in the project.	Understand the benefits offered by the PRO-CLIMATE methodology and ensure social acceptance. Understand and influence similar future projects. Participate in discussions and become active in climate resilience cases.

2.3 What to disseminate?

Within the framework of the PRO-CLIMATE project, there are several main project results that have been initially identified as important for dissemination and communication. These results are summarised in Table 3 below.

- A **living lab framework** to enable real-life environments for designing, implementing, testing, and monitoring systematic transformation to achieve climate resilience through behaviour changes and governance strategies.
- **Key drivers** and barriers of social transformation and behavioural change in the context of climate change adaptation at the community level.
- **Behavioural change process manual** for systemic transformations to climate resilience.
- **Conceptual model** of a European social-ecological system.
- **Web-based policy sandbox tool** (*includes the Multi Agent Computer Model (MACM) and the TransCliR tool*)
- Evidence-based **policy recommendations**, distilled in succinct policy guidelines that can be further adopted by both the project's as well as other European communities.

Table 3: PRO-CLIMATE list of results

Results	Type	Relevant WP	Indicator of success
A Living Lab framework to enable real-life environments for designing, implementing, testing, and monitoring systematic transformation to achieve climate resilience through behaviour changes and governance strategies.	Framework	WP2	Setup and run six (6) Living Labs Evaluation of each Living Lab operations Knowledge exchange between the Living Labs Sustainability of the Living Labs after the end of the project
Key drivers and barriers of social transformation and behavioural change in the context of climate change adaptation at the community level.	Report	WP3	Identification of stakeholders, critical thresholds, tipping points and feedback loops. Roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders. Collective choice arrangements. Framework under which behavioural changes are understood and analysed.
Behavioural change process manual for systemic transformations to climate resilience.	Manual	WP4	Toolkits to raise change capability at individual, organisational, and institutional level.

<p>Web-based policy sandbox tool</p> <p><i>includes the Multi Agent Computer Model (MACM) and the TransCliR tool</i></p>	<p>Web-based software</p>	<p>WP5</p>	<p>A conceptual model of a European social-ecological system</p> <p>MACM customised to a specific case study</p> <p>Software prototype incorporating the parameters of six (6) case studies</p> <p>Web-based policy sandbox tool making TransCliR tool accessible to local policy makers and relevant stakeholders</p>
<p>Evidence-based policy recommendations resulting from project work and from the case studies, distilled in succinct policy guidelines that can be further adopted by other European communities.</p>	<p>Policy recommendations</p>	<p>WP6</p>	<p>Seven (7) policy papers (one for each case study and one at the European level).</p>

2.4 When to Disseminate and Communicate

To ensure the optimal timing to engage in any sort of dissemination and communication activities, the PRO-CLIMATE consortium has identified three different time phases for its publicity and dissemination plan, where different activities have been assigned to different phases of the project: **early in the project**, **during the project** and at the **end of the project**, with the aim to constantly review and update this strategy according to the progress and new findings of the project.

More specifically:

- **Early in the project** dissemination aims to ensure that the project is addressing the needs of its target groups, and that it is creating awareness and understanding of its activities both within the consortium and among peer groups. A dialogue mechanism with the target groups has already been initiated, enabling them to provide constant feedback during this early phase, mainly via social media, the project website, and during the full course of the project.
- **During the project** dissemination is about identifying lessons, particularly in receiving feedback from target groups and stakeholders, and adjusting the project's strategy and developed components in order to maximize effectiveness and efficiency. At this stage, it is important to inform the research community and policy makers about the first results of the project and ensure appropriate peer review. Moreover, online communication activities will ensure wide participation of the target audiences in the project's activities (co-design, co-creation activities, interviews, surveys, coaching circles, focus groups, project events, workshops etc.).
- **At the end of the project** dissemination will publicize more generally the project's outputs, the lessons learnt, and the benefits gained. The dissemination activities will focus on building up a constituency of support for the project's follow-up activities, as well as on providing evidence to support the exploitation and sustainability of the PRO-CLIMATE methods and tools (especially the tools developed in WP5).

2.5 How to Disseminate and Communicate

To ensure the effectiveness of the PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication plan, its foundations should lay on the profiles of the target audiences and communication content should be formulated into coherent messages. Given that the target groups identified in Section 2.2 above, cover a wide variety of sectors (from policy makers to NGOs, SMEs chambers of commerce, researchers, general public) a segmented dissemination and communication plan is needed per target group.

The dissemination and communication plan is based on two levels of strategies for the dissemination and communication of the project's results and its progress:

- The consortium's **overall strategy**, that is the dissemination and communication strategy in which the consortium plans and acts.
- The **individual strategy** of each consortium member, according to its specific type of organisation, infrastructure, role and resources in the project, etc.

The dissemination and communication strategy includes activities that can be divided into internal and external dissemination and communication according to the target audiences they are addressed to.

Internal dissemination and communication include the instruments and activities that intend to raise awareness about the results destined for the consortium members and that are not available to the public in general. This kind of dissemination includes:

- Project meetings and their resulting reports (physical, virtual).
- Information exchange e.g., through mailing lists.
- A collaborative workspace document repository.
- Reports, publications, deliverables, etc.
- On-line collaboration through different means e.g., dissemination report form submission, regular WP and Task related meetings, online documents collaboration, blog posts and comments from partners, doodle polls etc.

External dissemination and communication refer to activities and means which create awareness of the project's partial and overall results and document the project's progress. The target of those dissemination activities is specific users and interest groups that have been identified above as well as the general public. PRO-CLIMATE proposes a mixed approach for the effective dissemination of its aims and results, facilitated by a variety of activities, both external and internal and is based on:

- Achieving reputation or a "name in the field" by using the media (including social media), speaking at conferences, and other relevant events, publishing articles to scientific journals or to the media;
- Networking - making and sustaining personal contacts and "selling" the project to stakeholders that can prove to be useful contacts;
- Capturing the interest of existing initiatives;
- Visiting decision making units and attending to EC workshops and info days;
- Liaison and clustering with other projects;
- Being contactable, accessible, open, and creative.

In the PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication strategy, **social media** and the **project website** play a key role. These online dissemination tools act as channels to promote cooperation with other projects and initiatives and generate engagement with key stakeholders through a real feedback channel, which in turn creates valuable assets for future projects. The aforementioned methods and channels will facilitate the sustainability of the project's solutions and prepare the market for their use.

All consortium members engage in communication activities locally, within the context of their countries to reach local, regional, European and international audiences. Additionally, in line with the proposal's sex and gender analysis, partners are committed to removing unintentional gender biases

in their communication tools and actions, aiming to communicate project activities and results in a gender-inclusive way.

2.5.1 Logo and Visual Identity

An essential part of building a brand is designing and creating a suitable logo to ensure the recognition of the project and communicate its identity to the stakeholder groups and the public in general. For this reason, the PRO-CLIMATE consortium created a project logo that reflects the overall concept of the project and its scientific domain of activity. All PRO-CLIMATE dissemination materials, documents, presentations at events and conferences, and online channels should include the project logo in high quality.

Figure 2 illustrates the PRO-CLIMATE logo that represents several important values that the project aims to convey:

- **Earth and environment focus:** The central image of the Earth signifies the project's dedication to global environmental issues and climate change. It emphasizes the planet as the focal point of the project's efforts.
- **Connectivity and collaboration:** The network-like design around the Earth suggests interconnectedness, symbolising the collaborative efforts required to tackle climate change. This could represent the joining of various stakeholders, including local entities, policy makers, SMEs, and individuals, in a united effort.
- **Simplicity and Clarity:** The clean, simple design of the logo helps to communicate the project's mission clearly and effectively. The straightforward design can make the logo more memorable and recognisable.
- **Green Colour Scheme:** The use of green is often associated with nature, sustainability, and environmental friendliness. This colour choice reinforces the project's commitment to eco-friendly and sustainable practices.
- **Modern Aesthetic:** The modern design aesthetic of the logo helps to appeal to a contemporary audience, emphasizing that the PRO-CLIMATE project is forward-thinking and innovative in its approach to addressing climate change.

Overall, the logo is designed to encapsulate the essence of the PRO-CLIMATE project by highlighting its focus on the environment, the importance of community collaboration, and the use of modern, clear, and eco-friendly design elements.

Figure 2: PRO-CLIMATE logo

2.5.2 Document and presentation templates

Clean and functional document and presentation templates are essential to achieve harmony and coherence among the many different results that project partners create throughout the project. In order to deliver a consistent message to all target audiences and facilitate the recognition of the graphical identity of the project, templates for both text documents and presentations were developed and made available to all consortium partners. Those templates include the PRO-CLIMATE deliverables template (Figure 3), and the PRO-CLIMATE presentation template (Figure 4).

Figure 3: PRO-CLIMATE deliverable template

Figure 4: PRO-CLIMATE presentation template

2.5.3 Promotional material

During the first year of the project, PRO-CLIMATE will design and produce a variety of promotional materials (leaflets, rollup banners, factsheets, infographics etc.), in electronic and hard-copy format to attract the attention and interest of its targeted groups.

On the second and third years of the project these materials will be updated according to the progress and advances of the project. Hard copies of the promotional materials will be made available for distribution to events. However, the PRO-CLIMATE consortium will avoid unnecessary printing / use of paper.

Examples of the leaflet and rollup designs created until M6 of the project are presented in the following figures:

D7.1 Publicity and Dissemination Plan first version

Figure 5: PRO-CLIMATE leaflet v1

Figure 6: PRO-CLIMATE leaflet v2

Figure 7: Rollup banners

2.5.4 Press releases

Within the framework of the PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication activities, appropriate press releases for announcements concerning the news and advances of the project will be developed. The project will produce the necessary press releases with regards to the project's course, the outcomes, the new elements and results of the case studies, the publications, etc. The consortium has already prepared and shared a first press release (<https://pro-climate.eu/pro-climate-press-release/>) regarding the kick-off of the project.

Funded by the European Union

PRO-CLIMATE
Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change

PRO-CLIMATE Horizon Europe project kicked-off

On the 1st of January 2024 the Horizon Europe project called PRO-CLIMATE officially kicked-off. The full name of the 3-years duration project is "Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change" and it was approved for funding in the frame of the Horizon Europe Research Programme (call topic "HORIZON-CL5-2023-D1-01-09: Behavioural change and governance for systemic transformations towards climate resilience").

PRO-CLIMATE aims to support communities to proactively adapt to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE will identify social tipping points and policy actions that enable systemic transformation to be achieved across social systems. PRO-CLIMATE will adopt an approach guided by the concept of systems thinking, which views communities as complex systems that are interconnected and influenced by multiple factors, socio-economic and environmental. By understanding and leveraging their dynamics, it will then develop strategies and interventions that promote social transformation and behavioural change. This will result in a robust framework for designing effective methodologies and tools to foster proactively adaptive behaviours and facilitate transformative changes.

A set of diverse (in terms of climate change problems and socio-economic contexts) case studies across Europe will be an instrumental tool for the co-creation, validation, and upscaling of this framework by running living labs and bringing stakeholders together to understand community governance and institutional structures, and to also pilot and validate the project's behaviour change activities.

The PRO-CLIMATE consortium consists of 10 partners from 7 countries, with excellent experience in all the tasks defined for PRO-CLIMATE. It represents a unique and true interdisciplinary group of highly competent and experienced research teams composed specifically for the project.

To learn more about our project you can visit our [website](#) and you can [subscribe](#) to our newsletter.

Key facts	Online presence
📅 Starting date: 1/1/2024	🌐 https://pro-climate.eu
📅 Duration: 36 months	📧 @PRO_CLIMATE_EU
💰 EC funding: €3,666,685	📌 #proclimateproject
👥 10 partners / 7 EU countries	📄 pro-climate-project

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Figure 8: PRO-CLIMATE 1st press release

2.5.5 Newsletters

During PRO-CLIMATE project's duration, six newsletters (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36) will be prepared and shared with the subscribed users and will be also published on PRO-CLIMATE's website. Circulating the project newsletter will guarantee target groups are reached not only within the partners' network but also within a larger community of interested potential users. The newsletter will include news and upcoming events, publications and report project's achievements. Also, the project will seek regular presence in already established newsletters.

The project's newsletter sign-up form was created via Mailchimp and is accessible through the project's website (Figure 9). Mailchimp is a privacy enhancing, GDPR-compliant platform, that allows subscription of interested users to the project's mailing list, while respecting all privacy policies that apply in such instances.

Join the **PRO-CLIMATE** community

Enter your email

I agree to my email being stored and used to receive the PRO-CLIMATE newsletter

Send

Figure 9: Newsletter subscription form

2.5.6 Project website

One of the most essential dissemination and communication tools of PRO-CLIMATE project is the project’s website, whose preliminary version launched on M1 of the project (January 2024). The website’s domain name is <https://pro-climate.eu>. All the necessary information regarding the progress of the project as well as project news, materials, etc. will be continuously uploaded on the project’s website. In particular, the PRO-CLIMATE website aims at:

- Providing information about the project, its main objectives, description of the produced outputs and knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which PRO-CLIMATE will participate, information about project partners with a link to their websites, subscription to project’s newsletter, social networks and contact info.
- Presenting information to stakeholders so that they will understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project’s activities.

Figure 10 is a screenshot of the PRO-CLIMATE website on its current form. The website features a clean and modern aesthetic. The design utilises a harmonious colour palette dominated by greens and blues, reflecting environmental themes. The layout is intuitive and user-friendly, with well-organised sections and clear navigation. Visual elements, such as images and icons, are used effectively to complement the textual content and highlight key information. Overall, the website's aesthetic aligns well with its mission of promoting climate awareness and action through a professional and approachable design.

Figure 10: PRO-CLIMATE website

2.5.7 Social Media

The PRO-CLIMATE consortium recognizes the crucial role of social media channels as integral components of its dissemination and communication strategy. These platforms can help the project raise awareness, engage communities, share project updates, foster collaboration and mobilise action especially with regards to climate issues. More specifically:

- **LinkedIn** page (<http://linkedin.com/company/pro-climate-project/>) will serve as a platform for raising awareness and engaging with academic professionals.
- **Facebook** page (<https://www.facebook.com/proclimate.project>) targets an audience aged 40 and above.
- **X (Twitter)** page (https://x.com/PRO_CLIMATE_EU) caters to fast-track individuals, news disseminators, and unofficial ambassadors, fostering synergies for informal dissemination and communication.

Furthermore, the upcoming official YouTube channel under PRO-CLIMATE will serve as a repository for storing all the videos to be produced during PRO-CLIMATE's implementation and beyond.

The social media accounts are managed and updated by Tero while all partners are responsible to provide content that would possibly interest the target groups. Moreover, partners are strongly encouraged to disseminate the project's social media posts via their own online channels. Particularly, the content that will be posted may include (*but not limited to*):

- PRO-CLIMATE public **deliverables**;
- PRO-CLIMATE **press releases**;
- PRO-CLIMATE **newsletters**;
- PRO-CLIMATE **publications** (including available links);
- Highlights from participation in **events and conferences**;
- **Outreach activities** (workshops, demonstrations, other events) organised by the consortium;
- **Liaison activities** (synergies) with other projects;
- Updates and insights from **project meetings**;
- Promotional **materials**;
- Detailed descriptions and results from **case studies**;
- **Success stories** and testimonials from project participants;
- Interactive **polls, surveys, and questionnaires** to engage the key audiences;
- Behind-the-scenes content showcasing the **project's progress and team dynamics**.

Using customised content to each platform, PRO-CLIMATE social media accounts are going to be used to increase project's visibility in social networking sites. The use of specific hashtags (#) enables interested parties to be informed about the project's activities and news. Indicatively, the hashtags that are most frequently used for the project's social media posts are:

- #climatechange
- #socialtransformation
- #behaviouralchange
- #socioecologicalsystems
- #environmental
- #climateresilience
- #socialtippingpoints

The social networking pages will be constantly updated throughout the whole duration of the project by adding content and news.

2.5.8 YouTube Channel and PRO-CLIMATE videos

In PRO-CLIMATE, at least two (2) videos will be produced (M7-M9 and M31-M33) to spread a message in a pertinent and easy to understand manner to a wider audience. The videos will be

uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel and shared on social media pages and the website. The content can be unique, produced for the purposes of disseminating a specific message about project related matters and/or derived from webinars, courses, live videos, or self-hosted partners’ videos.

At least two (2) videos regarding PRO-CLIMATE progress will be produced, to promote the project and provide information about the PRO- CLIMATE community. More specifically:

- The first video will present the project rationale and challenges, showcasing the problem and describing the envisioned solutions.
- The second video will present an overview of the needs and a demonstration of the PRO-CLIMATE solutions under various scenarios taken from the case studies.

2.5.9 Publications

Publications are a significant element of PRO-CLIMATE’s dissemination strategy, since they constitute a dissemination tool that informs and engages the PRO-CLIMATE community about the projects’ procedures, methodologies and outcomes. The projected body of reports conducted by project partners, not only fuels the project’s development but also facilitates its dissemination planning.

Overall, publications involve two overlapping elements:

Deliverable Reports: A considerable volume of partners work efforts is focused on conducting research and producing reports. This material is valuable in terms of effective dissemination of the project’s contribution. All public deliverables will be uploaded on an open access repository supported by the European Commission, Zenodo. The PRO-CLIMATE project has already established the PRO-CLIMATE Zenodo community, which can be accessed through the following link: <http://zenodo.org/communities/pro-climate/>.

Scientific Publications: Drawing from the above report material, project partners will be devoted in the creation of scientific articles published in the international scientific literature, when possible. All partners acknowledge their common interest in publishing the knowledge to obtain recognition and to advance the state of knowledge in the field. In this respect, any partner who is considering preparing a publication for a scientific magazine, is strongly encouraged to contact other partners in order to work together in this publication. Especially when the content of the publication is a product of the collective work of the consortium (or of a sub-group of partners), the names of the respective people and partners should appear on the publication.

The entire PRO-CLIMATE Consortium must approve all papers submitted for publication in conferences, journals, or media. If a publication is to be submitted, the consortium should be informed as soon as possible. The following procedure ensures that no paper will be submitted without the knowledge of the consortium, that the project will not be misrepresented, and that no confidential information will be unintentionally disclosed.

The consortium has drafted a non-exhaustive list of scientific journals where PRO-CLIMATE partners can publish scientific publications, as seen in Table 4.

Table 4: List of scientific journals

Journals	Publisher
Cities ¹	Elsevier B.V., Netherlands
Discover sustainability ²	Springer

¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/cities>

² <https://link.springer.com/journal/43621>

International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management ³	Emerald Group Publishing Ltd., UK
International Journal of Human Resource Management ⁴	Routledge, UK
Journal of Climate ⁵	American Meteorological Society, USA
Journal of Environmental Management ⁶	Elsevier B.V., Netherlands
Journal of Organizational Behavior ⁷	John Wiley and Sons Ltd, UK
Nature Climate Change ⁸	Nature Publishing Group, UK
Sustainability ⁹	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI), Switzerland
Sustainable Cities and Society ¹⁰	Elsevier B.V., Netherlands
Science of the Total Environment ¹¹	Elsevier B.V., Netherlands
The British Journal of Sociology ¹²	London School of Economics and Political Science
Current Sociology ¹³	Sage Journals
Gender and Society ¹⁴	Sage Journals
Society & Natural Resources ¹⁵	Taylor & Francis

All peer-reviewed scientific publications arising from PRO-CLIMATE project must be made available in **open access**. This implies that publications will be made freely available online, immediately upon publication and with no restrictions on use, by depositing them on a repository. The consortium should be aware that they are required to retain sufficient intellectual property rights (IPR) to comply with these open access obligations.

There are two ways to ensure immediate open access:

1. Deposit PRO-CLIMATE publications in a repository for scientific publications and ensure open access.
2. Publish PRO-CLIMATE research in an open access journal.

The consortium intends to upload at the latest at the time of publication (i.e. no embargo period), a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication (i.e. Author Accepted Manuscript - AAM; or author's postprint) in a trusted repository for scientific publications, with a CC-BY or equivalent license for articles (at least for the AAM); or with a CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND or equivalent license prohibiting commercial use or derivative works, for monographs and other long texts, with information about any research outputs, tools or

³ <https://www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/journal/ijccsm>

⁴ <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/riih20>

⁵ <https://www.ametsoc.org/index.cfm/ams/publications/journals/journal-of-climate/>

⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-environmental-management>

⁷ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10991379>

⁸ <https://www.nature.com/nclimate/>

⁹ <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability>

¹⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/sustainable-cities-and-society>

¹¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/science-of-the-total-environment>

¹² <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/14684446>

¹³ <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/CSI>

¹⁴ <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/GAS>

¹⁵ <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/usnr20>

instruments necessary to substantiate the conclusions of the scientific publication. Moreover, the consortium will aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publication.

2.5.10 Events database

In combination with the above tools and channels, PRO-CLIMATE is going to be promoted to the community of its stakeholders through participation in relevant conferences, workshops and other events organized by third parties. Such events offer a significant opportunity for PRO-CLIMATE to be disseminated in environments where key stakeholders are gathered. Hence, it is valuable for the project's development and impact to participate in events organised by international agencies, fora and institutions which present an expertise around the same scientific domain. Apart from conferences and workshops, which constitute the main types of events by third parties, project partners can also take part in varying events, like networking events, symposia and/or even webinars.

This part of dissemination and communication strategy depends on the good practices between project partners in terms of inner-project communication. That is, partners should share information they receive about upcoming events that present a subject closeness to PRO-CLIMATE's activities, thus updating the consortium about new dissemination and networking possibilities. Communicating such information can result to partners assisting other partners and collaboratively boost the project's impact on the projected areas of stakeholders.

The consortium maintains a detailed list of potential events that can be targeted for disseminating the project's results. The list is constantly updated and will be also available online in the following url: https://pro-climate.eu/relevant_events/. A snapshot of the most relevant events marked from July until the end of 2025 are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: List of relevant events that PRO-CLIMATE can participate

List of upcoming events	
European Sociological Association Conference 2024	27-30 August 2024
Open Living Lab Days 2024 ¹⁶	25-27 September 2024
NetworkNature Annual Event 2024 ¹⁷	25 September 2024
3rd World Conference on Climate Change & Sustainability ¹⁸	21-23 October 2024
Conservation Social Science Conference 2024 ¹⁹	20-23 November 2024

2.5.11 Cooperation and clustering with other projects

An essential part of PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication strategy is to establish synergies and natural links with other EU-funded projects and relevant initiatives. Networking activities foster a culture of co-operation between relevant stakeholders and help the development of a more efficient and attractive European Research Area.

¹⁶ <https://openlivinglabdays.com>

¹⁷ <https://networknature.eu/networknature-annual-event-2024-busting-myths-people-nature>

¹⁸ <https://climateweek.thepeopleevents.com/>

¹⁹ <https://scbsocialscience.org/2024conference/>

More specifically, PRO-CLIMATE will build a network of EU projects and will set up a knowledge sharing and transfer mechanism and will ensure long-term impact and sustainability of the network. Under this mechanism the PRO-CLIMATE project will ensure that synergies are identified and where possible exploited and regular collaboration is encouraged. Joint activities to be implemented include a) coordination in certain deliverables, b) coordination in the communication strategy, c) common working groups, and d) co-design approach. Special attention will be given to the Mission on Adaptation, the related Climate Change projects and its Mission Implementation Platform as well as the community of practice (CoP). PRO-CLIMATE's milestone no. 5 "Action plan for joint activities with other EU projects" (deadline M18) is relevant to this activity. The whole process will be coordinated by "Task 7.4: Cooperation and clustering with other projects" (M1-M36).

PRO-CLIMATE has already established close cooperation with NEUROCLIMA²⁰ (funded under the same topic) and established a communication channel with both AGORA²¹ and CLIMAS²² projects. More intensive work under this task is expected to progress further during the 2nd year of the project and collaborative events/project meetings are expected to occur.

PRO-CLIMATE has already established a link with the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) and is exploring collaboration opportunities. Collaboration with ENoLL is considered important for the sustainability and exploitation potential of the established Living Labs. ENoLL is also organising the European Open Living Lab days (OLLD), an annual event that attracts many relevant stakeholders. PRO-CLIMATE will be participating to these annual events and will be exploring opportunities to present the project results.

2.5.12 Events organised by the project

A broad agenda of events, including several workshops and round table meetings, is foreseen by the project, addressing all its targeted stakeholders, disseminating its outcomes across Europe. Some indicative events that will be organised during the project are the following:

Table 6: Events organised by PRO-CLIMATE

Description	Relevant Task	Timing	Participants	Type of event
Training workshops (6) for the change agents who will be responsible for implementing the pilot operational plans	Task 4.2	M8-M10	Change agents	Physical
Living Lab workshops (6) with the identified stakeholders to develop pilot operational plans to build the Climate Adaptation Strategies of the Living Labs.	Task 2.2	M9-M11	Living Labs	Physical
Training session (1) for LL leaders on participatory methodologies	Task 3.4	M12	All partners	Online
Workshops (6) for change process	Task 4.3	M12	LL members and change agents	Physical
Workshops (6) for change process for aligning good governance measures with	Task 4.3	M16	Change agents and	Physical

²⁰ <https://www.neuroclima.eu>

²¹ <https://agoraproject.eu>

²² <https://www.climas-project.eu/>

the intended behavioural change in each Living Lab			relevant stakeholders	
Workshops on Climate Transitions, Behavioural Science, and Good Governance Pathways for the Living Labs	Task 2.3	M21-M22	LL members	Physical
MACM workshop (what if scenarios)	Task 5.2	M21	All partners and relevant stakeholders	Physical
Workshop on policy recommendations	Task 6.2	M22	All partners and relevant stakeholders	Online
SWAP SHOP I workshops (6)	Task 4.4	M22	Change Agents and LL members	Physical
MACM web version design workshop	Task 5.2	M26	All partners and relevant stakeholders	Physical
Review, Refresh, Reset workshop	Task 4.4	M26-M27	Change Agents and LL members	Physical
Workshop on revision and fine-tuning of the policy recommendations	Task 6.3	M32	Policy makers, civil society organisations, journalists and business enterprises	Online
SWAP SHOP II workshops (6)	Task 4.4	M31-M32	Change Agents and LL members	Physical
Workshops (6) on Knowledge Management and Sustainability Plans for the Living Labs	Task 2.4	M33-M34	LL members	Physical
Final project event	WP7	M36	All relevant stakeholders	Physical

2.5.13 EU Adaptation Community (Mission)

PRO-CLIMATE project has already been invited to be part of the “Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change”. This community is now hosted on Futurium, a European Commission platform dedicated to discussions on EU policies. Benefits for PRO-CLIMATE to be part of this community are the following:

1. Wealth of resources, Thematic Working Groups, and collaboration opportunities specifically designed to support and enhance the success of PRO-CLIMATE.

2. A dedicated section where Mission Projects can promote their resources, such as guides, toolkits, best practices, and templates for other members of the Community, including regions and local authorities.
3. A platform for Mission Projects to showcase their successes, milestones, and impact under Resources and Outputs. Whether PRO-CLIMATE reached a goal, completed a significant project milestone, or achieved a positive outcome, can share the success stories with fellow members and inspire others in the community.
4. Whether PRO-CLIMATE is seeking advice, sharing lessons learned, or looking for potential collaborators, the new website provides a supportive environment for collaboration and knowledge sharing among Mission Projects.

3 Summary of Dissemination and Communication activities

The PRO-CLIMATE consortium has planned the Dissemination and Communication activities and set the targets for their performance. The performed activities will be constantly measured and monitored for their success in accordance with the related indicators. Table 7 shows the planned communication activities, as well as the indicators to evaluate the success of the dissemination and communication strategy.

Table 7: Summary of dissemination and communication activities

Objective	Actions required	Result indicator
Create the project's graphical identity	Development of the project logo	1 original logo
	Graphical design of the flyers and the posters	Year 1: At least 1 flyer, 1 rollup banner, 1 project card Year 2, Year 3: Update these materials based on the progress of the project
	Graphical design of the project website	The project's website will be designed according to the latest UI standards.
	Design of the documents and the presentation templates	About 4 templates for project documents, reports, and presentations.
	Design of the project presentation	1 project presentation that can be used by all partners for presenting the project Year 1, Year 2, Year 3: constant update to reflect the progress of the project.
Create the project's online presence	Project website	Year 1: ~250 monthly visits Year 2: ~500 monthly visits Year 3: ~750 monthly visits Total > 12.000 visitors

	News items	<p>News items will be published on a constant basis to present progress of the project.</p> <p>Year 1: 1 news item per month</p> <p>Year 2, Year 3: at least 2 new items per month</p>
	Social media accounts	<p>Year 1: At least one post per week and 200 followers on Twitter, 200 Likes on Facebook, and 200 followers on LinkedIn</p> <p>Year 2: At least two posts per week (300 followers on Twitter, 300 Likes on Facebook, and 300 followers on LinkedIn)</p> <p>Year 3: At least two posts per week (500 followers on Twitter, 500 Likes on Facebook, and 500 followers on LinkedIn)</p>
	PRO-CLIMATE project videos	<p>The first video will present the project rationale and challenges, showcasing the problem and describing the envisioned solution (M9-M12).</p> <p>The second video will present an overview of the needs and a demonstration of the PRO-CLIMATE solutions under various scenarios taken from the case studies (M34)</p>
	Zenodo community	All public deliverables and all public PRO-CLIMATE datasets
Project progress and results	Publications	<p>≥ 3 journal publications</p> <p>≥ 20 conference publications</p> <p>≥ 10 magazine publications</p>
	Newsletters	≥6 newsletters
	Press releases	≥3 press releases with
Networking activities	Participation in conferences, workshops and other relevant events	40 such interventions are foreseen during the project's lifetime
	Meetings with stakeholders	Separate meetings will be conducted with stakeholders in

		order to gather appropriate feedback.
	Synergies with other projects and initiatives (e.g. ENoLL)	10 synergies are targeted.
Events organised by the project	Workshops	=50 workshops with Living Labs, change agents, relevant stakeholders (See also Section 2.5.12)
	Interviews	~40 interviews with key stakeholders
	Online surveys, questionnaires	>200 number of participants
	Final project conference	1 event in Brussels with 50-100 participants

4 Calendar of Dissemination and Communication activities

The calendar in Table 8 includes the initial planned dissemination and communication activities in chronological order (quarterly). By M6 (June 2024) the consortium has already implemented the following actions:

- Design of the visual identity of the project (brand identity, logo, colours).
- Preparation of the official document and presentation templates (Word template for deliverables and agenda, Power Point template for presentations).
- Development of the first version of the project presentation (PowerPoint presentation / content and design).
- Setup of the project's social media channels (X, Facebook, LinkedIn).
 - https://x.com/PRO_CLIMATE_EU
 - <https://www.facebook.com/proclimate.project>
 - <http://linkedin.com/company/pro-climate-project/>
- Designed and developed the project website (<https://pro-climate.eu>).
- Designed the first versions of the project **flyer** (3fold), project **rollup banner**, project **card**.
- Published its 1st **press release**.
- Established the first **synergies** with sister projects (NEUROCLIMA, AGORA, CLIMAS) and the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL).

Table 8: Calendar of dissemination and communication activities

Quarters	Activity	Lead partner / contributor
Q1 <i>Jan – Mar 2024</i>	Visual identity	Tero
	Document and presentation templates	Tero
	Social media set up	Tero
	Website launch	Tero
	1st Press Release published	Tero, All partners

	Contact with sister project NEUROCLIMA	Tero
Q2 <i>Apr– Jun 2024</i>	4 social media posts / month	Tero
	2 news items on the website / month	Tero
	Calendar of events on the website	Tero, All partners
	Project flyer, rollup banner, card	Tero
	Finalisation of first draft of D7.1 Publicity & Dissemination Plan (PDP)	Tero
Q3 <i>Jul – Sep 2024</i>	1st newsletter	Tero
	1st video produced for project's promotion	Tero
	4 social media posts / month	Tero / All partners
	2 news items on the website / month	Tero / All partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero
Q4 <i>Oct – Dec 2024</i>	4 social media posts / month	Tero / All partners
	2 news items / month	PR&More / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero
	First plan for scientific publications	ATU
	Updated description of the Living Labs on the project website	Tero, All Living Labs
	Promotional Material translation in partners languages	All partners
	Results of the first workshops published on the project website	CU, ATU
Q5 <i>Jan – Mar 2025</i>	6 social media posts / month	Tero / All partners
	3 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero / all partners
	2nd Newsletter	Tero / all partners
	Updated plan for Scientific publications	ATU / All scientific partners
Q6 <i>Apr – Jun 2025</i>	2nd Press Release	Tero / all partners
	6 social media posts / month	Tero / all partners

	3 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	Promotional Material Update (Y2)	Tero / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero / all partners
Q7 <i>Jul – Sep 2025</i>	6 social media posts / month	Tero / all partners
	3 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	3rd Newsletter	Tero / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero / all partners
Q8 <i>Oct – Dec 2025</i>	6 social media posts / month	Tero / all partners
	3 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero / all partners
Q9 <i>Jan – Mar 2026</i>	6 social media posts / month	Tero / all partners
	3 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	4th Newsletter Issue	Tero / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero / all partners
Q10 <i>Apr – Jun 2026</i>	6 social media posts / month	Tero / all partners
	3 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero / all partners
	Promotional Material Update (Y3)	Tero / all partners
Q11 <i>Jul – Sep 2026</i>	6 social media posts / month	Tero / all partners
	3 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	5th Newsletter Issue	Tero / all partners
	2nd project video	Tero / all partners
	Liaison with other similar HE projects	Tero / all partners
Q12 <i>Oct – Dec 2026</i>	3rd Press Release	Tero / all partners
	8 social media posts / month	Tero / all partners
	2 news items / month	Tero / all partners
	6th Newsletter Issue	Tero / all partners

	Liaison with other similar HE projects	All partners
	Final Conference	Tero / all partners

5 Monitoring and evaluation

PRO-CLIMATE elaborates a specific evaluation strategy to monitor its dissemination and communication efforts and targets to reach. The goal is to provide concrete evidence about the effectiveness of the publicity and dissemination plan, as well as insights on how to amplify its reach and impact. Tero as Communication as well as Innovation and Exploitation Manager, ATU as Dissemination Manager will coordinate the efforts of all partners to support the process of creating the best possible impact.

To this end, Tero as WP7 leader, is responsible for overseeing the progress of the overall PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication activities. The monitoring and evaluation tools will assess the efforts in both qualitative and quantitative fashion. The procedures to be implemented are the following:

1. **Action plan creation and communication inside the consortium.** A specific list of activities will concentrate all the projected dissemination and communication actions which partners have to undertake. This list will comprise pre-defined and scheduled tasks, but it will also include partners individual plans for dissemination and communication activities which due to their nature cannot be precisely pre-organised, like the participation to upcoming conferences and networking events. This database will organise the activities on their whole in order for each partner to know what they are supposed to do and when. In addition, based on this inclusive schedule partners will receive bimonthly updates by Tero, as WP7 leader, about their dissemination and communication tasks.
2. **Dissemination and communication activities reporting by all partners.** When an opportunity for a dissemination activity emerges partners should notify WP7 leader (Tero) about it. Tero will document such action accordingly and provide any necessary assistance (e.g., guidelines, tips for better communication etc.). What is more, upon the completion of any form of their assigned dissemination activity, partners have to report the activity on the online PRO-CLIMATE Dissemination and Communication Activities Report tool so that a robust tracking of dissemination and communication efforts is made.
3. **Monitoring of participation in events.** As mentioned above activities within the dissemination and communication framework will be carefully evaluated in order to ensure the best possible dissemination of the project. Examples of such monitoring include guidelines to participating partners to inform them on how to communicate PRO-CLIMATE (tips for photos taken from events, PRO-CLIMATE rollup banner, flyers, etc.) and/or assistance with presentations preparation.
4. **Statistics of visibility, traffic, reach and engagement rates of PRO-CLIMATE's website and social media platforms.** This will allow partners to better understand the most appropriate timing, communication style and target audience of each message. Furthermore, such metrics are essential for planning re-adjustments.

To produce an accurate monitoring and evaluation procedure, as well as to recognise the impact of the actions carried out, it is essential for all partners to register the activities that they implement on time and correctly. Therefore:

- All partners should prepare their dissemination and exploitation activities according to their personalised action plan;
- All partners should report every dissemination and communication activity they are implementing or contributing to on time by registering them in the online dissemination and communication reporting tool (internal Google spreadsheet);
- All partners should save enough evidence of the completed activities;

- A monitoring tool with the planned and the target activities is used by WP7 leader.

5.1 Monitoring procedure: Reporting and Feedback

In PRO-CLIMATE, all project partners are obliged to report any communication and dissemination activities they implement. This is achieved through an internal online spreadsheet that has been created to keep track of the dissemination and communication activities implemented throughout the project. The dissemination and communication reporting tool is available on the project's internal repository and can be accessed by all consortium partners. The online reporting spreadsheet follows the Horizon Europe template for reporting dissemination and communication activities.

5.2 PRO-CLIMATE guide on dissemination and communication

This informal guide acts as a reminder checklist for partners to contribute to the project's publicity and dissemination plan during the whole project duration. It will be crosschecked by WP7 leader during every consortium meeting where a relevant presentation of dissemination activities will take place.

The PRO-CLIMATE dissemination and communication guide is comprised of the below enlisted guidelines, according to which project partners should:

1. Report on the online Dissemination and Communication Activities Report tool (or briefly via email to WP7 leader) any dissemination or communication activity related to PRO-CLIMATE, e.g., presentation, publication, participation in event, etc.
2. Inform WP7 leader about relevant events, where PRO-CLIMATE partners could participate (e.g., conferences, seminars, workshops etc.), so that the events database can be regularly updated. If necessary, arrangements could be made so that PRO-CLIMATE will be represented.
3. Collect photos, videos, from all PRO-CLIMATE activities (full documentation): meetings, workshops, seminars, press conferences, etc. Send them to WP7 leader to be used in publicity materials (e.g., news items on the project website, social media, project newsletters, videos, etc.). Make sure that there are no third party-intellectual property rights involved.
4. Use in all of the communication materials (deliverables, presentations, newsletters, etc.) the PRO-CLIMATE logo, the EU flag and the statement according to Article 17 of the Grant Agreement.
5. To avoid conflicts, co-ordinate with other partners and inform the consortium on intentions to publish from PRO-CLIMATE results. Always mention the financing body (EU / Horizon Europe).
6. Invite local policy makers in appropriate projects stages and inform them on project's progress. Record events (videos - photos). Send them to WP7 leader.
7. Forward press releases, newsletters and other materials to their contacts that might be interested to PRO-CLIMATE's objectives and thematic interests.
8. Contribute to PRO-CLIMATE's website's blog with an article about their work in the project, the progress, etc.
9. Provide material for regularly updating the PRO-CLIMATE website.
10. Follow PRO-CLIMATE's social media pages (Facebook, X, LinkedIn, YouTube). Monitor the announcements and posts, "like" them, comment on them. Make their own posts on PRO-CLIMATE's social media accounts. Connect with people. Initiate the dialogue or take part in it.